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To cite this article: Aline Schönenberg, Anna-Lena Küstner & Tino Prell (2026) Thinking it's boring in old age increases risk for future loneliness: findings from the German Ageing Survey (DEAS), *Aging & Mental Health*, 30:2, 325-335, DOI: [10.1080/13607863.2025.2545355](https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2025.2545355)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2025.2545355>

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Thinking it's boring in old age increases risk for future loneliness: findings from the German Ageing Survey (DEAS)

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Although often considered trivial, prolonged boredom is associated with apathy, cognitive decline, mental health problems, and social withdrawal. In older age, cognitive and health decline as well as shrinking social networks may increase boredom. Likewise, they lead to loneliness, a profound risk factor of health in older age. As aging stereotypes may diminish health and well-being, we aimed to understand whether thinking that aging means being bored (AAB) more often is linked with loneliness.

Methods: Using data on $N=2490$ older adults from two waves of the German Ageing Survey (DEAS, 2011 and 2017), we assessed whether AAB is a predictor of loneliness using generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs) and mediation analysis.

Results: About 11% of participants believe aging to be associated with increased boredom. Loneliness is exponentially increased the more participants expect boredom in age, even when controlling for sociodemographic, physical, and mental health data. There is a direct effect of AAB on loneliness but no indirect effects *via* depression or health.

Conclusion: Believing that aging is associated with boredom is independently linked with loneliness beyond mental and physical health. As ageing stereotypes may influence behaviour and well-being, psychosocial aspects must be incorporated for comprehensive geriatric care.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 28 April 2025

Accepted 1 August 2025

KEYWORDS

Boredom; older age; loneliness; social network; depression; mental health; older adults

Introduction

Although it may appear as a trivial, temporary dissatisfaction easily resolved by engaging in interesting activities, research indicates that chronic boredom is not at all trivial (Goldberg et al., 2011; Raffaelli et al., 2018; Ros Velasco, 2023). According to van Tilburg and Igou (2017), boredom is a negative emotion accompanied by low attention or activity and lack of meaningfulness that arises due to inner factors such as meaninglessness or motivational deficits, as well as outer factors like lack of stimulation or challenge. Boredom can be separated from other negative emotions like depressiveness or anhedonia and contributes individually to well-being (Goldberg et al., 2011; van Tilburg & Igou, 2017; Yeung et al., 2024). As summarized by Raffaelli et al. (2018), boredom manifests as a subjective experience of either restlessness or apathy and a growing disinterest in life. Described as a profoundly negative and unpleasant feeling (Martin et al., 2006), boredom has been linked to anger, sadness, and frustration (van Tilburg & Igou, 2012), culminating in cognitive problems, and depressive and anxious symptoms (Isacescu et al., 2017; Sommers & Vodanovich, 2000). Individuals prone to boredom often experience a loss of control over their

environment, have lower physical activity levels, and report poorer health (Mercer-Lynn et al., 2013).

While much research has been done to assess boredom in adolescence or at the workplace (Britton & Shipley, 2010; Cummings et al., 2016), the shrinking physical capacity for activities, cognitive decline, and social contacts makes boredom a relevant topic of older age. A common perception in society is that aging leads to increased boredom (Yesavage et al., 1982); thus, an underexplored aspect is the association between boredom and views of aging (VOA) (Bai, 2014). VOA can be understood as a concept of expectations and experiences regarding advancing age that inform how persons behave and feel as they age. VOA may concern both the personal experience with growing older and the societal consensus on aging (Diehl et al., 2014; Kornadt et al., 2020). Understanding societal attitudes toward aging is crucial because positive views can enhance the utilization of resources, whereas negative stereotypes can lead to discrimination and mistreatment (Kornadt et al., 2020). On a personal level, individuals who internalize negative stereotypes about aging often suffer worse health outcomes (Westerhof & Wurm, 2018), including poorer memory, hearing, and increased depressive symptoms (Bowen et al., 2020).

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 Supplemental data for this article can be accessed online at <https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2025.2545355>.

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Negative VOA further go hand in hand with resignation and lack of activity; for example, individuals who endorse the belief that older age is associated with boredom are less likely to proactively combat boredom when it arises (Nagamatsu et al., 2014). Particularly in advanced age, when combined with restrictions in health, functional ability, and control, boredom may lead to a loss of interest in life and further withdrawal (Isacescu et al., 2017; Raffaelli et al., 2018), making boredom a serious issue in an already vulnerable population. Much vagueness exists in the definition of boredom, which can be either considered a state occurring when performing a certain task, or a trait overduring a longer period of time; likewise boredom can be considered at the level of frequency, intensity, or as a holistic attitude concerning all aspects of life (Mercer-Lynn et al., 2013; Raffaelli et al., 2018; Tam et al., 2021). When considering boredom as an aging stereotype, meaning an apparently inevitable aspect of older age, a certain stability is introduced to the construct as VOA are known to be consistent (Wurm et al., 2025). Thus, linking boredom with VOA defines boredom as part of aging expectations that endure in situation-unspecific ways, going into the direction of overall 'life boredom' as described by Tam et al. (2021).

Loneliness is another prevalent condition that has a significant impact on both mental and physical health in older generations (Bowen et al., 2020; Huxhold & Henning, 2023). It is a risk factor for various long-term health issues, including anxiety, depression, dementia, and mortality (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015; Park et al., 2020). Factors contributing to loneliness include social relationships, physical health, and societal factors such as age and gender (Dahlberg et al., 2022), while Barnes et al. (2022) conclude that persons most likely to suffer from loneliness and social isolation are female, older, and with worse health status. Loneliness, distinct from being alone or socially isolated, is the subjective feeling of inadequate social connectedness (Hawkley & Cacioppo, 2010). While loneliness only constitutes one factor associated with the broad topic of social connectedness, which should be considered as a multi-faceted construct along with social isolation (Holt-Lunstad, 2025), loneliness as a subjective feeling has been shown to be more closely related with other self-rated mental health outcomes (Hong et al., 2023). While considering objective factors such as network size is important to gain a holistic understanding of social connectedness, it is still of interest to understand the subjective impressions that shape a person's interpretation of their social relationships and lead to perceived loneliness. Recognized as a public health issue, loneliness requires early identification of its predictors to develop effective public policy measures (Cacioppo & Cacioppo, 2018; Jeste et al., 2020).

Although this has not yet been scientifically tested, it is plausible that individuals who believe ageing to be

associated with boredom may experience reduced motivation to engage socially (Shiovitz-Ezra et al., 2018), greater emotional withdrawal, and lower expectations for meaningful activities (Raffaelli et al., 2018)—all of which may increase the risk of loneliness. However, to date, little is known about the relationship between the VOA that aging is associated with increased boredom and subsequent loneliness. Furthermore, as depressive symptomology influences both boredom (Ros Velasco, 2021) and loneliness (Erzen & Çikrikci, 2018; Park et al., 2020), the association between these variables may further be mediated by psychological distress. Depressive symptoms include lack of joy while performing activities, social withdrawal, and lack of motivation (Fiske et al., 2009; Kok & Reynolds, 2017; WHO, 2004), both of which may lead to increased boredom as activities are no longer engaging (Raffaelli et al., 2018), and to loneliness due to social withdrawal and lack of motivation to participate. Additionally, in older adults, participation in social settings as well as performance of general activities may be limited by declining health (Iburg et al., 2023; Wettstein et al., 2020). Therefore, health restrictions *via* self-rated health (SRH) should be incorporated in this context, as it reflects both objective health status and subjective well-being, and is a well-established correlate of loneliness and age-related outcomes (Wurm et al., 2017).

Given the adverse outcomes associated with loneliness, it is crucial to understand its influencing factors in advancing age. As VOA shape behaviour, they constitute an important hub for social activities. Negative VOA in general and boredom in particular may be related to loneliness due to social withdrawal and lack of meaning; therefore, it is essential to understand their impact on loneliness. This study thus aimed to examine whether endorsing the belief that aging entails increased boredom is a predictor of loneliness. To delimitate boredom from other potent influencing factors on loneliness, depressive symptoms should be assessed. Likewise, social network size as an objective measure should be included to arrive at an encompassing understanding of social connectedness. Both network size and depressive symptoms may serve as covariates to understand the pathways by which loneliness and boredom are linked. Using longitudinal data from the German Ageing Survey (DEAS), we sought to clarify the pathways through which age-related stereotypes such as increased boredom may influence psychosocial outcomes in later life.

Materials and methods

Samples

The data used in the analysis were taken from the German Ageing Survey (DEAS), a population-based survey of adults between 40 and 85 years of age living in private households in Germany (Klaus et al., 2017).

The survey was first conducted in 1996; additional waves followed every 6 years. The current study encompassed data from 2011 and 2017. We used these waves to avoid the potential influence of the COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on both boredom and loneliness. Data was collected from $N=4,854$ (wave 2011) and $N=6,626$ (wave 2017) participants. Only participants for whom data for loneliness were available were used for the following analyses ($N=3,916$ in wave 2011 and $5,540$ in wave 2017). From these, 2,490 participated in both waves.

Measures

Views on ageing: ageing means to me that I am bored more often (AAB)

In the DEAS survey, a single-item measure was included to assess boredom: Participants rated their agreement that "Ageing means to me that I am bored more often" (AAB) on a four-point rating scale encompassing 1 (strongly agree, AAB1), 2 (agree, AAB2), 3 (disagree, AAB3), and 4 (strongly disagree, AAB4), where higher values reflect a more positive VOA.

Loneliness

Loneliness was assessed with the 6 items version of the original scale to measure loneliness (de Jong Gierveld & van Tilburg, 2008). The scale includes three positive and three negative statements that respondents can agree or disagree with on a four-point scale from 1 (strongly agree) to 4 (strongly disagree). After recoding of items 2, 4 and 6, an average value is calculated ranging from 1 (loneliness low) to 4 (loneliness high) (Huxhold & Henning, 2023). To differentiate between the subjective feeling of loneliness and the more objective social isolation, we additionally included the network size as a covariate in our analyses.

Covariates

Based on the existing literature, several covariates associated with loneliness and views on aging were extracted from the dataset (Bai, 2014; Cacioppo & Cacioppo, 2018; Dahlberg et al., 2022; Hawkey & Cacioppo, 2010; Kornadt et al., 2020; Park et al., 2020). The covariates are detailed in the DEAS manual (https://www.dza.de/fileadmin/dza/Dokumente/Forschung/FDZ_DEAS-Doku/DEAS2017_2.2_User_Manual.pdf).

- Gender may impact VOA, loneliness, and boredom due to differences in tasks, personality, and socialization; thus, we included sex (0 = male, 1 = female) as covariate (Barreto et al., 2021; Diehl et al., 2021; McIntosh, 2006)
- As the probability of loneliness is known to vary across the lifespan (Mund et al., 2020), and the experience of boredom may also

increase with age (Plummer, 2019), we included age (years) as a covariate

- Self-rated health (SRH): SRH reflects a persons' rating of their overall health, and it influences social participation, aging perception, and boredom proneness (Diehl et al., 2021; Tomida et al., 2024). In the DEAS, participants were asked to rate their current health ('How do you rate your present state of health?') on a five-point Likert scale, with responses including 1= Very good, 2=Good, 3=Average, 4=Bad, 5=Very bad (Fayers & Sprangers, 2002).
- Social network size: Indicates the number of important persons with regular contact, included to measure objective social isolation
- Depressive symptoms: To differentiate boredom from other emotional states, it is important to consider depressive symptoms (Goldberg et al., 2011). Thus, depressive symptoms were assessed with the German Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression (CES-D) Scale (Radloff, 1977). The CES-D includes 15 items on depressive symptoms in the last week, providing a sum score ranging from 0 to 45, higher values indicate more depressive symptoms.

Statistical analyses

All analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS statistics (Version 27) and R (version 4.1.1, R, 2024). Descriptive statistics were used to characterize the participants.

To examine the longitudinal relationship between VOA and loneliness over time, Generalized Linear Mixed Models (GLMMs) were implemented using the 'lme4' package. The first model included AAB as the primary predictor, controlling for the wave (2011, 2017) while accounting for random intercepts at the individual level to capture between-person differences. Models were controlled for age, sex depression, social network size, and SRH. Model fit was evaluated using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). Missing data were treated with listwise deletion process.

To test whether depression and social network size mediate the effect of AAB on loneliness, a Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach was employed using the 'lavaan' package (Rosseel, 2012). The mediation model estimated the direct effects of AAB on loneliness, as well as indirect effects through depression and social networks, adjusting for age and sex. To assess whether AAB2011 predicts changes in loneliness from 2011 to 2017 *via* changes in depression and social networks, we structure the mediation model longitudinally, ensuring that: AAB is measured at baseline (2011), depression and social networks are measured at both time points (2011

and 2017), loneliness is measured at both time points (2011 and 2017), the mediators predict changes in loneliness from 2011 to 2017, and baseline loneliness (2011) is included as a control variable to separate within-person changes from between-person differences. Standardized estimates were reported. Model fit was assessed using comparative fit index (CFI), root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), and standardized root mean square residual (SRMR).

All analyses were conducted with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The characteristics of the participants are given in Table 1. In 2011, almost 11% of the included participants agreed (9.5%) or strongly agreed (1.4%) that ageing means that one is bored more often (AAB).

Table 1. Characteristics of people who participated in both waves.

Variable	2011		2017	
	M	SD	M	SD
Loneliness	1.74	0.51	1.74	0.53
Age	63.56	10.12	69.48	9.89
Social network size	5.15	2.67	5.13	2.74
Depression	6.11	5.83	6.48	5.73
	N	%	N	%
Sex				
Male	1422	48.7	1422	48.7
Female	1499	51.3	1499	51.3
Ageing means to me that I am bored more often				
Strongly agree	24	1.0	24	1.0
Agree	202	8.2	215	8.6
Disagree	1144	46.5	1147	46.0
Strongly disagree	1092	44.4	1109	44.4
State of health				
Very good	271	9.3	186	6.4
Good	1426	48.9	1311	45.1
Average	999	34.2	1129	38.8
Bad	192	6.6	228	7.8
Very bad	31	1.1	55	1.9

Table 2. GLMM comprehensive results.

Predictor	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	2.07 (0.06)*	2.30 (0.07)*	2.23 (0.07)*	2.19 (0.07)*
AAB2 (agree)	-0.04 (0.07)	-0.05 (0.07)	-0.06 (0.06)	-0.06 (0.06)
AAB3 (disagree)	-0.22 (0.06)*	-0.24 (0.06)*	-0.18 (0.06)*	-0.18 (0.06)*
AAB4 (strongly disagree)	-0.51 (0.06)*	-0.52 (0.06)*	-0.45 (0.06)*	-0.45 (0.06)*
Wave: 2017	0.09 (0.08)	0.10 (0.08)	0.04 (0.08)	0.03 (0.08)
AAB2:wave2017	-0.07 (0.09)	-0.07 (0.09)	0.01 (0.09)	0.01 (0.09)
AAB3:wave2017	-0.09 (0.08)	-0.09 (0.08)	-0.03 (0.08)	-0.02 (0.08)
AAB4:wave2017	-0.09 (0.08)	-0.09 (0.08)	-0.02 (0.08)	-0.02 (0.08)
Age	—	-0.0029 (0.0005)*	-0.0034 (0.0005)*	-0.0037 (0.0005)*
Sex	—	-0.043 (0.011)*	-0.064 (0.011)*	-0.062 (0.011)*
Depression	—	—	0.020 (0.0008)*	0.019 (0.0009)*
Network Size	—	—	-0.014 (0.002)*	-0.014 (0.002)*
Health State	—	—	—	0.023 (0.007)*
Model parameters and fit				
AIC	12,665.9	12,628	11,992.7	11,980.1
BIC	12,737.3	12,713.7	12,092.7	12,087.3
Random Effects σ^2	$\sigma^2 = 0.1049$	$\sigma^2 = 0.1051$	$\sigma^2 = 0.1050$	$\sigma^2 = 0.1046$
Intercept Variance	0.1438 (0.3792)	0.1423 (0.3772)	0.1229 (0.3506)	0.1232 (0.3510)

Standard errors in parentheses; * $p < 0.05$ AAB = Ageing means boredom.

Model 1: AAB only Model 2: AAB + Age & Sex.

Model 3: AAB + Age, Sex, Depression & NWsize.

Model 4: AAB + Age, Sex, Depression, NWsize & HealthState.

Notably, this distribution was stable between the two waves (Table 1).

We investigated the relationship between AAB and loneliness over time using GLMMs (Table 2). In Model 1, AAB was the sole predictor alongside time (wave) and their interaction. Higher AAB values (expecting less boredom) are significantly associated with lower loneliness. Participants who 'disagreed' (AAB3) with the AAB statement reported significantly lower loneliness levels ($\beta = -0.22$, $p < 0.001$), while those who 'strongly disagreed' (AAB4) showed an even greater reduction in loneliness ($\beta = -0.51$, $p < 0.001$). The lack of interaction between AAB and wave confirms the temporal stability of this protective effect.

Model 2 introduced age and sex as covariates and improved the model fit as indicated by a lower AIC (12,628 vs. 12,666). The relationship between AAB and loneliness remained, with both AAB3 ($\beta = -0.24$, $p < 0.001$) and AAB4 ($\beta = -0.52$, $p < 0.001$) predicting lower loneliness. Likewise, older age ($\beta = -0.0029$, $p < 0.001$) and female gender ($\beta = -0.043$, $p < 0.001$) were associated with lower loneliness.

Model 3 further included depressive symptoms and social network size as covariates, again improving model fit (AIC = 11,993 vs 12,628). The impact of AAB3 ($\beta = -0.18$, $p < 0.01$) and AAB4 (AAB4: $\beta = -0.45$, $p < 0.001$) on loneliness remained significant but was slightly attenuated. Depressive symptoms emerged as a predictor of higher loneliness ($\beta = 0.020$, $p < 0.001$), while larger social networks was protective against loneliness ($\beta = -0.014$, $p < 0.001$).

In Model 4, we lastly added SRH as a covariate, slightly improving overall model fit (AIC = 11,980). Notably, while worse SRH was linked to higher loneliness ($\beta = 0.023$, $p < 0.01$), it did not attenuate the effects of AAB3 ($\beta = -0.18$, $p < 0.01$) or AAB4 (AAB4: $\beta = -0.45$, $p < 0.001$) on loneliness. Likewise, the

association between depressive symptoms ($\beta=0.019$, $p<0.001$) and social network size ($\beta = -0.014$, $p<0.001$) persisted.

Ultimately, we aimed to understand how AAB and loneliness are linked and which of the covariates contribute to this effect. Therefore, the covariates that modulated the effect of AAB on loneliness in the previous results were included in the SEM mediation model as mediators. The longitudinal mediation analysis (see Supplement Table 3 for the model specification) aimed to determine whether the effect of AAB in 2011 on loneliness in 2017 was mediated by depression and social network size, while controlling for baseline loneliness, age, and sex (Table 3, Figure 1). Because SRH did not change the association between AAB and loneliness in GLMM, we did not include SRH in the mediation analysis. The structural equation model (SEM) fit was acceptable with a CFI of 0.950 and an RMSEA of 0.063, indicating a reasonably good model fit.

Figure 1 presents a visual summary of the SEM containing the levels of AAB (2, 3, and 4 in reference to 1), network size and depressive symptoms as potential mediators in 2011 and 2017, and 2017 loneliness. Links between the variables indicate direct effects, whereas links *via* a third variable represent indirect effects. Direct effects were again found between AAB and loneliness in 2017: individuals who agreed (AAB = 2) had a marginally significant effect (-0.220 , $p=0.035$), while those who disagreed (AAB = 3) and strongly disagreed (AAB = 4) showed

stronger reductions in loneliness (-0.228 , $p=0.021$; -0.266 , $p=0.008$, respectively). In line with the GLMM, this suggests that more positive VOA (less boredom) were directly associated with lower loneliness. Again, women show lower loneliness than men ($\beta = -0.053$, $p=0.002$), whereas age had no significant effect.

Examining the mediation effects, neither depressive symptoms nor social network size mediated the relationship between AAB and loneliness. This is because AAB was neither related to depressive symptoms (AAB3 \rightarrow *Depress_2017*: -1.556 , $p=0.250$; AAB4 \rightarrow *Depress_2017*: -2.244 , $p=0.097$) nor network size. However, both mediators independently affected loneliness: Depression in 2017 significantly increased loneliness ($\beta=0.019$, $p<0.001$), while a larger social network reduced loneliness ($\beta = -0.008$, $p=0.008$). This suggests that depression and social network size influence loneliness but do not partake in the effect of AAB. However, the total effects of AAB remained significant (AAB3: -0.262 , $p=0.017$; AAB4: -0.315 , $p=0.004$), confirming that the association between AAB and loneliness persists.

Discussion

Loneliness is a pervasive issue that impacts a considerable proportion of the population. It has been linked to a range of adverse outcomes, including negative effects on physical and mental health, quality of life, and mortality (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015).

Table 3. Mediation analysis.

Parameter	Estimate	Std.Err	z-value	p-value
Loneliness_2017 ~ AAB2 (c1)	-0.22	0.104	-2.113	0.035
Loneliness_2017 ~ AAB3 (c2)	-0.228	0.098	-2.313	0.021
Loneliness_2017 ~ AAB4 (c3)	-0.266	0.1	-2.672	0.008
Loneliness_2017 ~ Loneliness_2011	0.566	0.022	26.068	0
Loneliness_2017 ~ age	-0.001	0.001	-0.894	0.371
Loneliness_2017 ~ sex	-0.053	0.017	-3.026	0.002
Depress_2017 ~ AAB2 (a1)	-0.593	1.425	-0.417	0.677
Depress_2017 ~ AAB3 (a2)	-1.556	1.354	-1.149	0.25
Depress_2017 ~ AAB4 (a3)	-2.244	1.354	-1.658	0.097
Depress_2017 ~ Depress_2011	0.409	0.026	15.505	0
NWsize_2017 ~ AAB2 (a4)	0.351	0.479	0.733	0.464
NWsize_2017 ~ AAB3 (a5)	0.529	0.455	1.165	0.244
NWsize_2017 ~ AAB4 (a6)	0.566	0.455	1.245	0.213
NWsize_2017 ~ NWsize_2011	0.346	0.02	17.513	0
Loneliness_2017 ~ Depress_2017 (b1)	0.019	0.002	10.637	0
Loneliness_2017 ~ NWsize_2017 (b2)	-0.008	0.003	-2.668	0.008
Intercept Loneliness_2017	1.048	0.137	7.68	0
Intercept Depress_2017	5.88	1.352	4.348	0
Intercept NWsize_2017	2.801	0.448	6.25	0
Var Loneliness_2017	0.161	0.006	27.413	0
Var Depress_2017	27.503	1.282	21.446	0
Var NWsize_2017	6.585	0.152	43.311	0
Indirect AAB2 \rightarrow Depress \rightarrow Loneliness	-0.012	0.028	-0.415	0.678
Indirect AAB3 \rightarrow Depress \rightarrow Loneliness	-0.03	0.027	-1.138	0.255
Indirect AAB4 \rightarrow Depress \rightarrow Loneliness	-0.044	0.027	-1.628	0.104
Indirect AAB2 \rightarrow NWsize \rightarrow Loneliness	-0.003	0.004	-0.711	0.477
Indirect AAB3 \rightarrow NWsize \rightarrow Loneliness	-0.004	0.004	-1.074	0.283
Indirect AAB4 \rightarrow NWsize \rightarrow Loneliness	-0.005	0.004	-1.132	0.258
Total Effect AAB2	-0.234	0.115	-2.041	0.041
Total Effect AAB3	-0.262	0.109	-2.396	0.017
Total Effect AAB4	-0.315	0.111	-2.844	0.004

Note: AAB=Aging means boredom, 1=fully disagree to 4=fully agree. Depress=Depression, NWsize=Network size, Var=Variance.

Figure 1. Mediation analysis.

Note: D11/17: Depression Wave 2011/2017, L11/17: Loneliness Wave 2011/2017, NW11/17: Network Size Wave 2011/2017, AAB: Ageing means Boring scale levels 2, 3 and 4 in reference to 1. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

About 6% of our participants reported experiencing loneliness, which is consistent with the previous reports (Ong et al., 2016). At present, only estimates are available for certain regions and countries. For example, within European countries, Eastern European nations have higher rates of compared to Northern European nations (Yang & Victor, 2011). The discrepancies in methodologies may be a contributing factor to the observed discrepancies in the estimated figures. These include the type of measurement employed, the mode of data collection, the representativeness of the sampled population, and the inclusion criteria applied.

In light of the high prevalence of loneliness and its impact on physical, mental, and cognitive health (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015; Park et al., 2020), it is imperative to identify predictors of loneliness at an earlier stage in the aging process. Among the many risk factors for loneliness are negative VOA (Shiovitz-Ezra et al., 2018). Negative VOA encompass a range of stereotypes, including those related to physical decline, dependency, and irrelevance. These attitudes can result in the exclusion, discrimination, and marginalization of older individuals, which in turn impacts their mental health and well-being,

ultimately leading to feelings of loneliness (Menkin et al., 2017; Pikhartova et al., 2016). The promotion of positive portrayals of aging, the fostering of inter-generational connections, and the recognition of the diverse contributions of older individuals represent key strategies for addressing negative attitudes towards ageing (Kornadt et al., 2020; Wurm et al., 2017). Interestingly, in our results, age was not predictive of higher loneliness. In previous research, a U-shaped curve for loneliness across the lifespan has been observed, with increasing loneliness after the age of around 80 and upwards. In contrast, people around the age of 70 report some of the lowest loneliness scores across the lifespan (Barreto et al., 2021; Mund et al., 2020). Therefore, in our study with participants aged an average of 63 (Wave 2011) to 69 (Wave 2017) years old, age may not play a role for loneliness.

The specific VOA under investigation in the present analysis is the expectation that aging is associated with increased boredom. Previous research indicates that boredom among older adults is influenced by various sociodemographic factors, including the loss of functional capabilities or perceived lack of usefulness to others (Ros Velasco, 2023).

Although boredom can be attributed to external factors such as social isolation, financial constraints, or limited caregiving opportunities, it can also be attributed to internal components such as impaired cognitive function, lack of perceived meaning, or fatigue (Raffaelli et al., 2018). Boredom thus represents a risk factor for dignified aging, with prolonged boredom contributing to physical and psychological issues that compromise quality of life and health (Ros Velasco, 2023). Boredom is associated with the negative emotional states such as frustration, anxiety, and feelings of worthlessness (Raffaelli et al., 2018; van Tilburg & Igou, 2012), representing a significant issue for older adults. Furthermore, it can lead to mental health issues, a sense of helplessness, and increased feelings of loneliness (Ros Velasco, 2021). Boredom is a fundamentally negative experience that arises under over- and understimulation, when an engagement with the surroundings is either not possible due to cognitive overload, or not wanted, due to motivational deficits and anhedonia (Raffaelli et al., 2018). As these challenges are highly probable in advancing age, the objective of this study was to ascertain which factors are associated with the expectation that advancing age is associated with increased boredom. As boredom may be associated with social withdrawal and overall disengagement, we focused on examining the association between this expectation and feelings of loneliness.

Both the GLMM and the SEM results show that AAB was significantly associated with loneliness reduction, with stronger effects observed in those who strongly disagreed with the statement that aging leads to boredom. Adding depression and social network size to the model improved model fit, while the direct effect of AAB remained significant, suggesting that these factors did not fully account for the relationship between AAB and loneliness. The mediation analysis supports the GLMM findings in that AAB has a direct effect on reducing loneliness, and while depression and social networks are independent predictors of loneliness, they do not explain the protective effect of positive aging attitudes. This suggests other mechanisms may be responsible for why individuals with more positive VOA experience less loneliness over time.

The study findings indicate an association between the experience of boredom and loneliness in older adults. The perception that aging inevitably leads to boredom increases the likelihood of loneliness, which is a significant public health concern affecting both physical and mental well-being (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015; Jeste et al., 2020). When individuals internalize the belief that aging is synonymous with boredom, it creates an expectation that contributes to increased feelings of disengagement from life. This expectation

of boredom may lead to resignation when social contacts decrease and diminish motivation to engage in social or meaningful activities, which in turn leads to loneliness. In our results, individuals aged 60 and above who perceive aging as a precursor to boredom are more prone to disengage from social interactions, thereby intensifying feelings of loneliness. This may result in a vicious cycle where both boredom and loneliness reinforce each other. Older individuals, particularly those who are institutionalized or have reduced mobility, are especially susceptible to this cycle due to their limited access to engaging activities (Ros Velasco, 2021, 2023).

Of note, in our mediation analysis, depressive symptoms did not explain the connection between loneliness and boredom, despite boredom being perceived as a negative emotion. These results are in line with other research separating boredom from other emotional states such as sadness, apathy, or anhedonia, all of which are depressive symptoms (Goldberg et al., 2011; van Tilburg & Igou, 2012; 2017). One study in particular described a difference between depressiveness and boredom proneness in memory consolidation, indicating that depressiveness and boredom are separable constructs (Yeung et al., 2024). This is confirmed in our results where boredom remained a significant influencing factor on loneliness even when controlling for sociodemographic information, health, and mood. While both boredom and depressiveness contribute to loneliness, in our research, there is no direct influence between the two of them, highlighting that they describe independent states, perhaps differing in their burden and valence levels (van Tilburg & Igou, 2017). Thus, while they may co-occur and an effect of prolonged boredom on depressiveness has previously been shown (Isacescu et al., 2017; Lee & Zelman, 2019), it appears the two are not bidirectionally linked. Likewise, social network size did not mediate the effect between AAB and loneliness; despite being a strong predictor of loneliness, network size is not associated with AAB in our data. This missing link may be rooted in the cognitive nature of boredom which is described as a lack of meaningfulness or lack of engagement (van Tilburg & Igou, 2012); thus, it is plausible that boredom may not be linked with the number of social relationships but rather with the quality of them. To fully understand boredom and its association with loneliness, in future studies, other mediating variables such as control perception (Isacescu et al., 2017; Struk et al., 2021), anxiety (Isacescu et al., 2017), life purpose and satisfaction, or motivation and daily activities should be considered.

Of note, in line with the definition of boredom in the literature being vague (Raffaelli et al., 2018), the item on boredom utilized in this analysis enquired

after the general perception of boredom in advancing age. Other research, however, indicates that different types of boredom with different arousal levels may exist (Goetz et al., 2014), which may differ in prevalence, influence, and connection to other variables. Likewise, depressive symptoms are multi-faceted and range from sadness to lack of interest to physical symptoms and fatigue (WHO, 2023). Particularly, fatigue is highly prevalent in older age, and has previously been linked to boredom (Raffaelli et al., 2018), making it a potential target linking both. In future research, it may be beneficial to assess which individual symptom of depression is particularly linked with boredom (Schönenberg et al., 2024). While our data provides first insights into prevalence and impact of boredom in older age, to fully understand its characteristics and implications in advanced age, a more nuanced approach on boredom is needed.

The implications of these findings extend beyond the individual experience, indicating significant public health concerns. Both loneliness and boredom have been identified as risk factors for a range of adverse health outcomes (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015; Ong et al., 2016; Park et al., 2020; Wurm et al., 2017). This interconnection highlights the necessity for a comprehensive approach to geriatric care, addressing physical and emotional experiences of older individuals. In the care of older patients, it is of utmost importance to not only consider physical impairments but to address and improve mental health and social connectedness for healthy aging and sustained quality of life (Gajic et al., 2018). Educational campaigns to inform healthcare providers about the power of mental and social parameters, as well as measures to challenge aging stereotypes are important footholds for an improved geriatric care (Wyman et al., 2018). Our findings also have implications for cultural policy considerations. Negative VOA, such as the belief that it results in boredom and social irrelevance, contribute to the marginalization and social exclusion of older adults. Campaigns to promote growth-based VOA are crucial to globally improve aging perception and give room for their protective effects on well-being (Diehl et al., 2021; Westerhof & Wurm, 2018).

While this study provides novel insight into two important psychosocial predictors of well-being, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. Firstly, the use of self-reported data may introduce bias, particularly in relation to subjective experiences such as boredom and loneliness. This social desirability bias may lead to an underestimation of their actual prevalence or intensity. Secondly, the study's focus on German participants may limit the generalizability of the findings to other cultural or geographical contexts. VOA, boredom, and loneliness may vary significantly across cultures. Depending on a country's

socioeconomic status, proportion of older adults in society, and societal norms, VOA may vary (Karasawa et al., 2011). While perceptions of physical and cognitive decline were comparable, a study showed cultural differences in the perceptions of societal VOA depending on the role of older adults (Löckenhoff et al., 2009). Likewise, aging discrimination may vary between countries, with Germany showing lower levels of perceived discrimination compared to other nations (P. de Paula Couto et al., 2023). As Germany is an economically strong country with comprehensive health insurance, it is unclear how applicable these findings are to populations outside of Germany; studies should be repeated in socioeconomically weaker countries to assess the impact of aging perceptions.

Another limitation is the exclusion of individuals with severe illness from the sample, which may result in an underestimation of the prevalence of boredom and loneliness (Goodwin et al., 2023). Although the study demonstrates a robust link between AAB and loneliness, it is uncertain whether boredom is a direct causal factor in the development of loneliness or if both are manifestations of broader psychosocial or health concerns in aging populations. Future studies should include other variables in addition to network size and depressiveness to uncover the variables that link AAB and loneliness. In the same fashion, the direction of effects between AAB and loneliness may also be present in reverse, with loneliness leading to increased boredom. As loneliness is an important health issue that impacts the health of older adults and thus needs to be targeted in clinical interventions, we aimed to assess the factors it is associated with, in this case boredom. However, the reverse direction is also probable, as it is also likely that boredom may occur more frequently when nobody is around to speak with, do activities with and share life with. The lack of mediation between AAB and either network size or depressive symptoms may be due to the direction of effects: Boredom and depressiveness as well as network size may bidirectionally impact each other, potentially nullifying the mediation effects. Additionally, the study's reliance on standardized scales may result in an oversimplification of complex experiences such as loneliness and boredom. These emotional states are complex and the standardized measures used may not fully capture the nuances of how different individuals experience them (Mercer-Lynn et al., 2013). Likewise, due to the design of the available data, only a single item assessed the level of boredom, reducing reliability and generalizability. In future studies, using a multitude of boredom measures including standardized questionnaires may provide a more robust and in-depth understanding of boredom and how it is linked with other emotional states. In conclusion,

while the study offers valuable insights into the relationship between boredom and loneliness in older adults, the limitations indicate a need for further research to confirm and expand upon these findings in order to arrive at a comprehensive understanding of older age and its related experiences.

Consent

Informed consent was obtained from all participants, see <https://www.dza.de/en/research/fdz/german-ageing-survey/data> for more information

Ethics approval

No ethics approval was required for the DEAS dataset according to the German Research Foundation. See <https://www.dza.de/en/research/fdz/german-ageing-survey/data> for more information.

Disclosure statement

The authors report that there are no competing interests to declare.

Data availability

The data used in this study stem from the German Ageing Survey (Deutscher Alterssurvey, DEAS). After registration, data is freely available for scientific use from <https://www.dza.de/en/research/fdz/german-ageing-survey>

Funding

There was no funding specific to this work. TP received funding from a Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF, Federal Ministry of Education and Research) grant (01GY2301).

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References

Bai, X. (2014). Images of ageing in society: A literature review. *Journal of Population Ageing*, 7(3), 231–253. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12062-014-9103-x>

Barnes, T. L., MacLeod, S., Tkatch, R., Ahuja, M., Albright, L., Schaeffer, J. A., & Yeh, C. S. (2022). Cumulative effect of loneliness and social isolation on health outcomes among older adults. *Ageing & Mental Health*, 26(7), 1327–1334. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2021.1940096>

Barreto, M., Victor, C., Hammond, C., Eccles, A., Richins, M. T., & Qualter, P. (2021). Loneliness around the world: Age, gender, and cultural differences in loneliness. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 169, 110066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2020.110066>

Bowen, C. E., Spuling, S. M., Kornadt, A. E., & Wiest, M. (2020). Young people feel wise and older people feel energetic: Comparing age stereotypes and self-evaluations across adulthood. *European Journal of Ageing*, 17(4), 435–444. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10433-019-00548-4>

Britton, A., & Shipley, M. J. (2010). Bored to death? *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 39(2), 370–371. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyp404>

Cacioppo, J. T., & Cacioppo, S. (2018). The growing problem of loneliness. *Lancet (London, England)*, 391(10119), 426. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(18\)30142-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(18)30142-9)

Cummings, M. L., Gao, F., & Thornburg, K. M. (2016). Boredom in the workplace: A new look at an old problem. *Human Factors*, 58(2), 279–300. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018720815609503>

Dahlberg, L., McKee, K. J., Frank, A., & Naseer, M. (2022). A systematic review of longitudinal risk factors for loneliness in older adults. *Ageing & Mental Health*, 26(2), 225–249. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2021.1876638>

de Jong Gierveld, J., & van Tilburg, T. (2008). [A shortened scale for overall, emotional and social loneliness]. *Tijdschrift Voor Gerontologie En Geriatrie*, 39(1), 4–15. (De ingekorte schaal voor algemene, emotionele en sociale eenzaamheid.) <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf03078118>

Diehl, M., Wahl, H. W., Barrett, A. E., Brothers, A. F., Miche, M., Montepare, J. M., Westerhof, G. J., & Wurm, S. (2014). Awareness of aging: Theoretical considerations on an emerging concept. *Developmental Review: DR*, 34(2), 93–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dr.2014.01.001>

Diehl, M., Wettstein, M., Spuling, S. M., & Wurm, S. (2021). Age-related change in self-perceptions of aging: Longitudinal trajectories and predictors of change. *Psychology and Aging*, 36(3), 344–359. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pag0000585>

Erzen, E., & Çikrikci, Ö. (2018). The effect of loneliness on depression: A meta-analysis. *The International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 64(5), 427–435. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020764018776349>

Fayers, P. M., & Sprangers, M. A. G. (2002). Understanding self-related health. *Lancet (London, England)*, 359(9302), 187–188. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(02\)07466-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(02)07466-4)

Fiske, A., Wetherell, J. L., & Gatz, M. (2009). Depression in older adults. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*, 5(1), 363–389. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.clinpsy.032408.153621>

Gajic, O., Ahmad, S. R., Wilson, M. E., & Kaufman, D. A. (2018). Outcomes of critical illness: What is meaningful? *Current Opinion in Critical Care*, 24(5), 394–400. <https://doi.org/10.1097/mcc.0000000000000530>

Goetz, T., Frenzel, A. C., Hall, N. C., Nett, U. E., Pekrun, R., & Lipnevich, A. A. (2014). Types of boredom: An experience sampling approach. *Motivation and Emotion*, 38(3), 401–419. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11031-013-9385-y>

Goldberg, Y. K., Eastwood, J. D., LaGuardia, J., & Danckert, J. (2011). Boredom: An emotional experience distinct from apathy, anhedonia, or depression. *Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, 30(6), 647–666. <https://doi.org/10.1521/jscp.2011.30.6.647>

Goodwin, V. A., Low, M. S. A., Quinn, T. J., Cockcroft, E. J., Shepherd, V., Evans, P. H., Henderson, E. J., Mahmood, F., Ni Lochlainn, M., Needham, C., Underwood, B. R., Arora, A., & Witham, M. D. (2023). Including older people in health and social care research: Best practice recommendations based on the INCLUDE framework. *Age and Ageing*, 52(6), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afad082>

Hawkey, L. C., & Cacioppo, J. T. (2010). Loneliness matters: A theoretical and empirical review of consequences and

- mechanisms. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine: A Publication of the Society of Behavioral Medicine*, 40(2), 218–227. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12160-010-9210-8>
- Holt-Lunstad, J. (2025). Social connection or loneliness? How we frame the issue may significantly impact public policy. *Health Psychology: Official Journal of the Division of Health Psychology, American Psychological Association*, 44(5), 560–562. <https://doi.org/10.1037/hea0001433>
- Holt-Lunstad, J., Smith, T. B., Baker, M., Harris, T., & Stephenson, D. (2015). Loneliness and social isolation as risk factors for mortality: A meta-analytic review. *Perspectives on Psychological Science: A Journal of the Association for Psychological Science*, 10(2), 227–237. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691614568352>
- Hong, J. H., Nakamura, J. S., Berkman, L. F., Chen, F. S., Shiba, K., Chen, Y., Kim, E. S., & VanderWeele, T. J. (2023). Are loneliness and social isolation equal threats to health and well-being? An outcome-wide longitudinal approach. *SSM - Population Health*, 23, 101459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmph.2023.101459>
- Huxhold, O., & Henning, G. (2023). The risks of experiencing severe loneliness across middle and late adulthood. *The Journals of Gerontology. Series B, Psychological Sciences and Social Sciences*, 78(10), 1668–1675. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/gbad099>
- Iburg, K. M., Charalampous, P., Allebeck, P., Stenberg, E. J., O’Caoimh, R., Monasta, L., Peñalvo, J. L., Pereira, D. M., Wyper, G. M. A., Niranjana, V., Devleeschauwer, B., & Haagsma, J. (2023). Burden of disease among older adults in Europe—trends in mortality and disability, 1990–2019. *European Journal of Public Health*, 33(1), 121–126. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckac160>
- Isacescu, J., Struk, A. A., & Danckert, J. (2017). Cognitive and affective predictors of boredom proneness. *Cognition & Emotion*, 31(8), 1741–1748. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02699931.2016.1259995>
- Jeste, D. V., Lee, E. E., & Cacioppo, S. (2020). Battling the modern behavioral epidemic of loneliness: Suggestions for research and interventions. *JAMA Psychiatry*, 77(6), 553–554. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2020.0027>
- Karasawa, M., Curhan, K. B., Markus, H. R., Kitayama, S. S., Love, G. D., Radler, B. T., & Ryff, C. D. (2011). Cultural perspectives on aging and well-being: A comparison of Japan and the United States. *International Journal of Aging & Human Development*, 73(1), 73–98. <https://doi.org/10.2190/AG.73.1.d>
- Klaus, D., Engstler, H., Mahne, K., Wolff, J. K., Simonson, J., Wurm, S., & Tesch-Römer, C. (2017). Cohort Profile: The German Ageing Survey (DEAS). *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 46(4), 1105–1105g. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyw326>
- Kok, R. M., & Reynolds, C. F.3rd. (2017). Management of depression in older adults: A review. *JAMA*, 317(20), 2114–2122. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2017.5706>
- Kornadt, A. E., Kessler, E.-M., Wurm, S., Bowen, C. E., Gabriel, M., & Klusmann, V. (2020). Views on ageing: A lifespan perspective. *European Journal of Ageing*, 17(4), 387–401. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10433-019-00535-9>
- Lee, F. K. S., & Zelman, D. C. (2019). Boredom proneness as a predictor of depression, anxiety and stress: The moderating effects of dispositional mindfulness. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 146, 68–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2019.04.001>
- Löckenhoff, C. E., De Fruyt, F., Terracciano, A., McCrae, R. R., De Bolle, M., Costa, P. T., Aguilar-Vafaie, M. E., Ahn, C.-k., Ahn, H.-n., Alcalay, L., Allik, J., Avdeyeva, T. V., Barbaranelli, C., Benet-Martinez, V., Blatný, M., Bratko, D., Cain, T. R., Crawford, J. T., Lima, M. P., ... Yik, M. (2009). Perceptions of aging across 26 cultures and their culture-level associates. *Psychology and Aging*, 24(4), 941–954. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0016901>
- Martin, M., Gaynor, S., & Stew, G. (2006). The phenomenon of boredom. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(3), 193–211. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qrp066oa>
- McIntosh, E. G. (2006). Sex differences in boredom proneness. *Psychological Reports*, 98(3), 625–626. <https://doi.org/10.2466/pr0.98.3.625-626>
- Menkin, J. A., Robles, T. F., Gruenewald, T. L., Tanner, E. K., & Seeman, T. E. (2017). Positive Expectations Regarding Aging Linked to More New Friends in Later Life. *The Journals of Gerontology. Series B, Psychological Sciences and Social Sciences*, 72(5), 771–781. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/gbv118>
- Mercer-Lynn, K. B., Flora, D. B., Fahlman, S. A., & Eastwood, J. D. (2013). The measurement of boredom: differences between existing self-report scales. *Assessment*, 20(5), 585–596. <https://doi.org/10.1177/107319111408229>
- Mund, M., Freuding, M. M., Möbius, K., Horn, N., & Neyer, F. J. (2020). The stability and change of loneliness across the life span: A meta-analysis of longitudinal studies. *Personality and Social Psychology Review: An Official Journal of the Society for Personality and Social Psychology, Inc*, 24(1), 24–52. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1088868319850738>
- Nagamatsu, L. S., Flicker, L., Kramer, A. F., Voss, M. W., Erickson, K. I., Hsu, C. L., & Liu-Ambrose, T. (2014). Exercise is medicine, for the body and the brain. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 48(12), 943–944. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2013-093224>
- Ong, A. D., Uchino, B. N., & Wethington, E. (2016). Loneliness and health in older adults: A mini-review and synthesis. *Gerontology*, 62(4), 443–449. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000441651>
- P. de Paula Couto, M. C., Nikitin, J., Graf, S., Fung, H. H., Hess, T. M., Liou, S., & Rothermund, K. (2023). Do we all perceive experiences of age discrimination in the same way? Cross-cultural differences in perceived age discrimination and its association with life satisfaction. *European Journal of Ageing*, 20(1), 43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10433-023-00790-x>
- Park, C., Majeed, A., Gill, H., Tamura, J., Ho, R. C., Mansur, R. B., Nasri, F., Lee, Y., Rosenblat, J. D., Wong, E., & McIntyre, R. S. (2020). The effect of loneliness on distinct health outcomes: A comprehensive review and meta-analysis. *Psychiatry Research*, 294, 113514. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113514>
- Pikhartova, J., Bowling, A., & Victor, C. (2016). Is loneliness in later life a self-fulfilling prophecy? *Ageing & Mental Health*, 20(5), 543–549. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2015.1023767>
- Plummer, B. A. (2019). Boring into the state of boredom through age groups: Types of boredom and strategies to increase motivation and positive life outcomes. In P. D. Keough (Ed.), *Ethical problem-solving and decision-making for positive and conclusive outcomes* (pp. 57–77). Information Science Reference. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-7582-5.ch004>
- R Core Team (2024). R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Radloff, L. S. (1977). The CES-D Scale: A self-report depression scale for research in the general population. *Applied Psychological Measurement*, 1(3), 385–401. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014662167700100306>
- Raffaelli, Q., Mills, C., & Christoff, K. (2018). The knowns and unknowns of boredom: A review of the literature. *Experimental Brain Research*, 236(9), 2451–2462. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00221-017-4922-7>

- Ros Velasco, J. (2021). The Experience of Boredom in Older Adults: A Systematic Review. 11. *Health, Aging & End of Life*, 6, 44. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8428388>
- Ros Velasco, J. (2023). Contemporary myths on boredom. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 8, 1183875. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsoc.2023.1183875>
- Rosseel, Y. (2012). lavaan: An R package for structural equation modeling. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 48(2), 36. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v048.i02>
- Schönenberg, A., Heimrich, K. G., & Prell, T. (2024). Impact of depressive symptoms on medication adherence in older adults with chronic neurological diseases. *BMC Psychiatry*, 24(1), 131. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-024-05585-7>
- Shiovitz-Ezra, S., Shemesh, J., & McDonnell/Naughton, M. (2018). Pathways from Ageism to Loneliness. In L. Ayalon & C. Tesch-Römer (Eds.), *Contemporary perspectives on ageism* (pp. 131–147). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-73820-8_9
- Sommers, J., & Vodanovich, S. J. (2000). Boredom proneness: Its relationship to psychological- and physical-health symptoms. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 56(1), 149–155. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(sici\)1097-4679\(200001\)56:1<149::aid-jclp14>3.0.co;2-y](https://doi.org/10.1002/(sici)1097-4679(200001)56:1<149::aid-jclp14>3.0.co;2-y)
- Struk, A. A., Scholer, A. A., & Danckert, J. (2021). Perceptions of control influence feelings of boredom [Original Research]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 687623. 2021 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.687623>
- Tam, K. Y. Y., van Tilburg, W. A. P., & Chan, C. S. (2021). What is boredom proneness? A comparison of three characterizations. *Journal of Personality*, 89(4), 831–846. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12618>
- Tomida, K., Shimoda, T., Nakajima, C., Kawakami, A., & Shimada, H. (2024). Social isolation/loneliness and mobility disability among older adults. *Current Geriatrics Reports*, 13(2), 86–92. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13670-024-00414-x>
- van Tilburg, W. A., & Igou, E. R. (2017). Boredom begs to differ: Differentiation from other negative emotions. *Emotion (Washington, D.C.)*, 17(2), 309–322. <https://doi.org/10.1037/emo0000233>
- van Tilburg, W. A. P., & Igou, E. R. (2012). On boredom: Lack of challenge and meaning as distinct boredom experiences. *Motivation and Emotion*, 36(2), 181–194. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11031-011-9234-9>
- Westerhof, G. J., & Wurm, S. (2018). *Subjective aging and health*. Oxford University Press.
- Wettstein, M., Wahl, H. W., & Siebert, J. S. (2020). 20-year trajectories of health in midlife and old age: Contrasting the impact of personality and attitudes toward own aging. *Psychology and Aging*, 35(6), 910–924. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pag0000464>
- WHO. (2004). *ICD-10: International statistical classification of diseases and related health problems: Tenth revision* (2nd ed.). World Health Organization. <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/42980>
- WHO. (2023). *Fact Sheet: Depressive disorder (depression)*. World Health Organization.
- Wurm, S., Diehl, M., Kornadt, A. E., Westerhof, G. J., & Wahl, H. W. (2017). How do views on aging affect health outcomes in adulthood and late life? Explanations for an established connection. *Developmental Review: DR*, 46, 27–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dr.2017.08.002>
- Wurm, S., Gehring, M., Blawert, A., Zok, K., Schröder, H., & Kornadt, A. E. (2025). Views on aging throughout the adult lifespan: Age grading in five dimensions. *GeroPsych*, 38(2), 61–70. <https://doi.org/10.1024/1662-9647/a000347>
- Wyman, M. F., Shiovitz-Ezra, S., & Bengel, J. (2018). Ageism in the Health Care System: Providers, Patients, and Systems. In L. Ayalon & C. Tesch-Römer (Eds.), *Contemporary perspectives on ageism* (pp. 193–212). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-73820-8_13
- Yang, K., & Victor, C. (2011). Age and loneliness in 25 European nations. *Ageing and Society*, 31(8), 1368–1388. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0144686X1000139X>
- Yesavage, J. A., Brink, T. L., Rose, T. L., Lum, O., Huang, V., Adey, M., & Leirer, V. O. (1982). Development and validation of a geriatric depression screening scale: A preliminary report. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 17(1), 37–49. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3956\(82\)90033-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3956(82)90033-4)
- Yeung, R. C., Danckert, J., van Tilburg, W. A. P., & Fernandes, M. A. (2024). Disentangling boredom from depression using the phenomenology and content of involuntary autobiographical memories. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 2106. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-52495-5>